

DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF A SMART HEALTH MONITORING SYSTEM

Parthib Banerjee¹, Soumayadeep Pal¹, Avrajeet Ghosh¹

¹B.Tech Student

²Susmita Das

*²Assistant Professor, Department of Electronics and Instrumentation Engineering
81, Nilgunj Road, Jagrata Pally, Deshopriyo Nagar, Agarpara, Kolkata, West Bengal
700109*

*{*Email – parthibban065@gmail.com}*

Abstract – Smart healthcare is important for people who need continuous monitoring that can't be provided outside a hospital. It is also important in rural areas and villages where nearby clinics can communicate with city hospitals and know the health status of their patients. This work demonstrates an intelligent health monitoring system that uses biomedical sensors to check patient conditions and uses the Internet to notify affected persons. The biomedical sensor here connects to his Arduino NANO controller to read data and then to an LCD display/serial monitor to see the output. The data is uploaded and stored on the server and converted into JSON links for viewing on smartphones. An Android application has been developed to allow easy viewing of patient information from doctors and family members.

Keywords – healthcare, monitoring, biomedical sensors, patient.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Health not only signifies the absence of disease but also a balance of complete physical, mental, and social well-being. Health is a fundamental part of people's quest for a better life. Unfortunately, certain factors such as poor health care, the existence of large disparities between rural and urban areas, and the unavailability of doctors and nurses during the most difficult times create dilemmas. increase. Connected. IoT has networked all objects internally in the last decade and is considered the next technological revolution. Smart health monitoring mechanisms [1, 2], smart parking [3], smart homes [4], smart cities [5], smart climate [6], industrialized land [7], agricultural sector [8], and IoT is part of Split. application. The largest use case for IoT is healthcare, providing the ability to track health and environmental conditions. IoT is nothing more than connecting computers to the Internet through sensors and networks [9, 10]. These connected components can be used in health monitoring devices. The sensors are used to transmit information to remote locations such as machines for computers, machines for humans, handhelds, or M2M such as smartphones [11]. It's a simple, energy-efficient, much smarter, scalable, and interoperable way to track and optimize healthcare. Today, modern systems offer flexible interfaces [12], tools [13], and mental health management [14] to guide people's mental lives. Heart rate and body temperature are the two most important indicators of human health. Heart rate is the number of heartbeats per minute, commonly known as pulse rate. Increased blood flow can be used to measure pulse rate by calculating pulse rate. A normal heart rate for a healthy person is 60

to 100 beats per minute. A typical resting heart rate for an adult male is approximately 70 beats per minute and for an adult female is 75 beats per minute [15]. Women over the age of 12 typically have higher heart rates than men. Human body temperature is just body temperature, and the total amount of heat emitted by the body is scientifically determined. The average person's body temperature depends on many factors, including ambient temperature, gender, and diet. In a healthy adult, he ranges from 36.5°C (97.8°F) to 37.2°C (99°F). Various factors can lead to changes in body temperature, such as B. Influenza, hypothermia, and other illnesses. Fever is the classic indicator of almost all illnesses [16]. There are various methods of determining heart rate and body temperature invasively and non-invasively. For consumers, non-invasive approaches have proven accurate and convenient for some time [17]. It has been suggested that medical facilities should provide good room conditions to support patients [18]. Several measurements determine the ambient quality of a room, such as the humidity of the room and the content of all gases such as CO and CO₂. Toxic gases and constant humidity are extremely harmful to patients. Indoor humidity should be between 30% and 65% for optimal comfort. Some studies [19, 20] have been done only for smart homes, not specifically for healthcare. There are several fatal diseases such as heart disease [21], diabetes [22], breast cancer [23, 24], and liver disease [25]. However, the main concern of the system we have developed is to monitor the basic symptoms and hospital room environment of all types of patients. This white paper proposes a custom healthcare system that monitors a patient's pulse and temperature, humidity, CO, and CO₂ gas levels in a hospital room.

1.1 OBJECTIVE

A smart health monitoring system using a smart automated ventilation system is an innovative approach to and promote healthy living. The system integrates advanced sensors and machine learning algorithms to monitor different aspects of health. Use data to adjust oxygen flow. In addition, the system can detect the health status of the occupants and warn if potential health hazards such as high CO₂ levels or low oxygen levels occur.

The system measures the heart rate, blood pressure, body temperature, and oxygen levels from its many sensors. These devices can provide real-time feedback to the system, enabling it to adjust the airflow and filtration based on the occupant's health status.

Benefits of a Smart Health Monitoring System using Smart Ventilation

Automatic Control: The system can automatically adjust the airflow and filtration based on real-time data, eliminating the need for manual intervention.

Health Monitoring: The system can monitor the health of occupants by integrating with wearable devices that can measure vital signs such as heart rate, blood pressure, and oxygen levels, body temperature.

Portable ventilation: This system can provide ventilatory support to an ICU patient. It helps patients to breathe during certain operation times. It will be also helpful in the rural area where ventilatory support for a patient is needed.

Early Warning: The system can detect and alert occupants of potential health hazards, allowing them to take preventive measures or seek medical attention promptly.

Real-time Monitoring: Smart health monitoring systems add visibility and predictability to our health conditions. Not only can you visualize your historic and current health conditions using statistics.

Healthcare service: The system can be used in hospitals, clinics, and other healthcare facilities to monitor patients' health and ensure optimal health status. The system can also integrate with electronic health records (EHR) to provide real-time data to healthcare providers and enable personalized care.

The technology behind a Smart Health Monitoring System using Smart Ventilation

Sensors: The system uses sensors to monitor various parameters such as temperature, humidity, O₂ in blood, and heart rate of the body. The sensors can be installed in different parts of the device for a different purposes.

Machine Algorithms: The system uses sensor data to adjust the oxygen flow and filtration system accordingly. The algorithms can also detect patterns and anomalies in the data, providing valuable insights into the occupants' health.

Wearable Devices: The system can integrate with wearable devices that can measure heart rate, blood pressure, and oxygen levels. The data from these devices can be used to adjust the oxygen flow and filtration based on the occupants' health status.

Furthermore, the smart health monitoring system can also integrate with healthcare providers' systems to track the occupant's health status and provide timely intervention in case of any abnormalities. This integration can provide valuable insights into the occupant's health, enabling healthcare providers to offer personalized care.

Overall, a smart health monitoring system using a smart ventilation system is a promising solution to promote healthy living.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

Figure 1: Schematic Diagram of Smart Health Monitoring System

The Arduino NANO being the heart of the complete system, controls all the coupled biomedical sensors and the servo motor to run the ventilation system. The complete system is powered by a 5v supply. The sensors connected to the Arduino produce analog serial values that are displayed on the LCD and depending on those values, the servo controls the intensity of ventilation. The ECG sensor is connected to the NodeMCU which, based on the sensor data displays the real-time graph in the mobile phone using Blynk IoT.

COMPONENT	DESCRIPTION	SPECIFICATION
Arduino NANO	Manifests data from nearly all the biomedical sensors connected and processes the same to generate a desired output.	3.3 V to 12 V I/O 1 A
Servo	A device used to convert electricity to precise and controlled movement using negative feedback.	6kgf at 4.8 V 10kgf at 10 V
Blood-O₂ Sensor	Provides electrical signals depending on the parameters it measures namely SpO ₂ level and pulse.	3.3 V I/O 1 A
Humidity	Generates electrical signals depending on the levels of humidity and ambient temperature.	5 V I/O 1 A
Temperature Sensor	Measures the real-time body temperature and provides electrical signals accordingly.	5 V I/O 1 A

LCD Display	Displays all the values manifested by the sensors such as humidity, temperature, Blood-O ₂ , etc.	5 V I/P 1 A
NodeMCU	A wi-Fi-based micro-controller unit is used to present real-time in graphical format over Wi-Fi to phones or laptops using software named Blynk .	3.3 V to 5 V I/O 1 A 2.4 GHZ max bandwidth
ECG Sensor	process the ECG signal and display the real-time graph to mobile phones via NodeMCU using Blynk IoT.	3.3 V I/O 1 A

Below is the complete circuit diagram of our project divided into two parts.

Part 01: This part of the circuit contains the sensors that manifest analog serial data which are directly displayed to the LCD display using the Arduino NANO.

Sensors Involved: Blood-O₂, Temperature, Humidity, and the servo-ventilation system.

Figure 2: Circuit Diagram of Ventilation System

Part 02: This part of the circuit contains the sensors that manifest data which are directly displayed to the mobile or computer screen via NodeMCU using Blynk IoT.

Sensors Involved: ECG Sensor, OLED Display.

Figure 3: Circuit Diagram of ECG sensor circuit

3.0 RESULT

The design has been finished with success with the utmost satisfaction. The constraints measured met and triumphed over with achievement. The system nominated is intended as find it infectious was set within the layout section. The design gives a clever plan for growing a full-fledged mileage fulfilling the person's needs. The device is extremely protean. This law encompasses an easy display screen that lets the person apply without any vexation. confirmation assessments iatrogenic have mainly dropped crimes. vittles are created to ameliorate the law. It has been examined with live records and has supplied a prosperous result. Thence the law has tested to determine expeditiously. The device created met its objects, with the aid of using being veracious to apply. This law is advanced with measurability in mind. farther modules can be different as soon as necessary. The law is advanced with a popular approach. All modules inside the device are examined with licit records and invalid records and the wholeness oils with achievement. still, there's nevertheless plenitude of compass for unborn development and accessories in practicality. A wide variety of the most bones being cell mileage enhancement for extraordinary cell software program package. It's displaying live videotape footage to the controlling person's device and the stir of the quadcopter is likewise great.

3.1 OBSERVATION TABLE

SpO ₂ LEVEL	SERVO	
	INPUT VOLTAGE	TIME DELAY
95 %	5 V	20 ms
92 %	5 V	18 ms
89 %	5 V	14 ms
86 %	5 V	12 ms
83 %	5 V	10 ms
80 %	5 V	8 ms

Table 02: Observation Table for researched data

3.2 FUTURE SCOPE

- The prototype could be matured with a storage device to remember the previous values of the patient and compare them with the current value to prescribe the best result.
- This could be advanced with voice AI support to help novice people handle this machine during an emergency.
- It could be fed with preset data for every illness and would work accordingly in automatic as well as manual mode of a particular patient.
- The could be reduced into a wearable gadget excluding the ventilation and to a mini backpack with ventilation for sudden on-the-way emergencies.

4.0 REFERENCES

N. V. Lopes, F. Pinto, P. Furtado, J. Silva. Iot architecture proposal for disabled people. 2014 IEEE 10th International Conference on WiMob, pages 152–158, Oct 2014.

I. Chiuchisan, H. N. Costin, and O. Geman. Adopting the Internet of Things technologies in health care systems. In 2014 International Conference and Exposition on EPE, pages 532– 535, Oct 2014.

B. G. Ahn, Y. H. Noh, and D. U. Jeong. Smart chair based on the multi-heart rate detection system. In 2015 IEEE SENSORS, pages 1–4, Nov 2015.

Smart health monitoring system. Published in 2017 International Conference on Information, Communication, Instrumentation, and Control (ICICIC), 5th Feb 2018.

Development of Smart Healthcare Monitoring System in IoT Environment. Available online, 26th May 2020, Md. Milon Islam, Ashikur Rahaman & Md. Rashedul Islam.

Knowledge-Based Intelligent Systems in E-Health and Medical Communication Services. Available online, on 16th Nov 2021, Mohammad Monirujjaman Khan, Safia Mehnaz, Antu Shaha, Mohammed Nayem, and Sami Bourouis.

IoT-Based Smart Health Monitoring System for COVID-19. Available online, 20th Jan 2022, Vaneeta Bhardwaj, Rajat Joshi, and Anshu Mli Gaur.

Smart Healthcare Monitoring using IoT. Available online, Shubham Banka¹, Isha Madan², and S.S. Saranya³.